

Interval Measurement Versus a Continuous Variable in Quantum Entropy Calculations Part III

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. and SPN, Messina Dec. 12, 2023

In Parts I and II, we considered the classical spatial probability $P(x)dx = dx/L$ for a particle with constant velocity/momentum and argued that this measure is linked to measurement because specific dx regions are required. We note that this measure may be used for a particle moving to the right or left, giving the impression that such motion is essentially the same, at least in terms of $P(x)$. In Part II, however, we argued that one cannot properly describe a particle with momentum p by giving $P(x)dx = dx/L$ and p . Here we try to describe the reason.

Velocity = dx/dt , which is again based on a spatial measurement interval dx . In such a measure, a particle moving to right has a positive dx , and to the left a negative. In other words, this is very much a translational picture of the center-of-mass point. The particle translates to the right or left smoothly and so $P(x)dx$ is the same. We argue, however, that a particle has a size, i.e. a front and back. If it moves to the right, density "is added" to the right of the front and disappears from the back and vice versa for motion to the left. This is a physical process which should be associated with motion and so a full description of spatial motion cannot be the same for motion to the right or left, we argue. Furthermore, this density shift occurs throughout the particle, not just at the back and front edges.

According to this scenario, we suggest, as in Part I, that p and $-p$ information has been removed from $P(x)dx = dx/L$ leaving a somewhat static, translational picture with no sense of particle size as part of the motion scenario. It is for this reason that we suggest a $P_{\text{special}}(p,x)$ in Part I which must differ from $P_{\text{special}}(-p,x)$, yet the two create the static $P(x)$ via $P_{\text{special}}(p,x)P(-p,x)$. In other words, we argue that $P(x)dx = dx/L$ is not a complete description of motion because it cannot distinguish between p and $-p$, which is tantamount to saying that it contains the common feature of both types of motion, namely that each x point, or rather dx interval, carries the same weight. A description using dx intervals is therefore incomplete, we argue. Information is already being thrown away at the classical level, namely information distinguishing motion to the right and left due to the finite size of a particle. $P(x)dx$ is an abstraction describing smooth flow motion and not a kind of periodic, remove density behind-add density in front picture. We have discussed such a type of motion in a previous note, but here we wish to show its connection with $P(x)dx = dx/L$.

A main consideration, however, is that if $P_{\text{special}}(p,x)$ is based on the physical consideration of density disappearing in one place and being added to another continuously, why isn't it associated with a dx interval measurement type picture. We suggest that it is the continuous nature of this process and its periodicity which lead to the dynamic $\exp(ipx)$ We explored this notion in Part II.

Newtonian Mechanics and the Interval Picture

We argue that the interval picture goes back to Newtonian mechanics which treats a particle as a point. If it has size, this point represents the center-of-mass and one may describe the relevant physics (i.e. changes of properties) of this center within an interval dx . In other words, one considers the average value of the property within dx to make the picture seem deterministic. Later, dx is shrunk to zero. This formalism is linked with measurements because a particle is said to spend a dt in an interval dx , i.e. have a velocity(x) while at the same time accelerating. The idea is that not only is the particle a point, but dx also shrinks to a point.

As a result, we argue that what could be an important physical feature of particle motion is removed, namely the periodic removal of density at the "back" and the addition of density at the "front" for motion to the right. This addition/removal picture suggests a kind of periodicity, while $dx/dt = \text{constant}$ suggests smooth translational motion in space. If the particle moves to the right, dx is positive, otherwise it is negative. In other words, there is smooth motion either to the right or left. We suggest that the removal-addition of density is different for motion to the right or left. This is a

physical statement and we argue that it should be manifested in a probability density in x, p . The usual probability density which appears in the literature (1), however, is based on the Newtonian interval picture. In Part I, it was noted that it is proportional to dt , even for motion in a region with a potential $V(x)$. For no potential, one has:

$$P(x,p)dx = dx/L \quad ((1))$$

This removes all information about p and so in Part I, we called it static. Here we note that it is more a description of the motion of the center-of-mass than one showing how a particle with size actually moves. We thus suggest, as in Part I, that there exists a $P_{\text{special}}(p,x)$ such that:

$$P_{\text{special}}(p,x)P_{\text{special}}(-p,x) = P(p,x) = 1/L \quad ((2))$$

The motion of $P_{\text{special}}(p,x)$ is directly linked to the particle and not the interval dx chosen. It must distinguish between p and $-p$. It is suggested that $P(p,x)$ describes the smooth translational motion associated with both center-of-mass motion to the right or left. In other words, probability in space for p or $-p$ is the same, and the motion is distinguished by dx , which is positive for forward motion and negative for backwards. Actual motion, however, is somewhat chunky and periodic with a distinct difference of forwards and backwards motion which goes beyond changing $+$ to $-$.

A problem which seems to appear at this point is that even though actual motion involves removing density from the back and adding it to the front for forward motion, different objects may have different shapes and sizes. This is why Newtonian mechanics uses the notion of center-of-mass in the first place. Although this is true, we argue removal of density in one place and its addition in another, leading to chunky periodic motion, is a key physical principle. As the object moves, regardless of its length and shape, density is removed from one region and added to another, not just at the back and front edges. Thus a periodic chunky description may be general and not tied to the shape of the object. Rather it is a feature of physical motion we argue.

In such a case, what does $P(x)dx=dx/L$ represent? It seems to represent the removal of the chunky periodic motion which is not needed in Newtonian mechanics in a description of the speed of the center-of-mass. Newtonian mechanics represents smooth motion in that dx intervals are shrunk to zero, yet changes occur within these dx intervals, e.g. acceleration. Newtonian mechanics then deals with relative behaviour within dx intervals, which are in principle measurable intervals and so cannot shrink to zero. We argue that this is the case, because for an accelerating particle, probability to be in an interval dx is proportional to dt , i.e.

$$P(x,p)dx = C dx/v(x) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is entirely interval based. In other words, one has a point which enters and then leaves an interval, whether it be a dx or dt interval. A particle, however, is not a point and is undergoing a physical chunky removal-addition of density type of motion, we argue. At the same time there is a mapping between such a chunky periodicity and the smooth translational one of ((3)) because it is indeed true that particles of different shapes may be described by a center of mass which moves smoothly. The center-of-mass, however, is an abstraction of a particle, and drops an important feature of the particle which has a finite size which, in fact, is associated with chunky periodic motion.

Center-of-Mass

An important feature of the center-of-mass is that it is a point which may be described precisely because one uses a Newtonian interval picture and leaves all the details within the interval. The center-of-mass has a velocity $v(x)$ at x in dx and an acceleration $a(x)$ also in dx . One may see that such a description already leaves out details of motion and changes in motion. The interval dx is the

measurement arena and one reports the average result $v(x)$ and then $a(x)$, not continuous motion. The argument is that the description becomes continuous when dx shrinks to zero, but it does not shrink to zero because one cannot do a measurement in a $dx=0$.

The chunky periodic motion of adding-removing density on the other hand is continuous, but it occurs throughout the moving object and so is hard to pinpoint classically. It is rather associated with probability, but due to ((2)) represents a kind of square root probability which is not directly associated with the measure dx . In other words, one is not doing any kind of measurement in dx .

This seems to lead to a dilemma. If one is able to describe the chunky periodic motion of removing/adding density classically, then why is it not represented mathematically in a classical manner as well? It seems that periodic chunky motion cannot describe a point and so has to describe dynamics within a region probabilistically. One cannot describe it classically because one would have to introduce dx intervals linked with measurements. A moving particle, however, is continuous and does not depend on outside measurements. One cannot remove its periodic chunkiness to approximate it by a center-of-mass point without losing critical information which is relevant to spatial impulse interactions.

Such a region holds regardless of the shape of the particle. It is dependent on its momentum. One wishes classically to see the particle as a point, i.e. its center-of-mass, so the center-of-mass is somehow linked with probabilistic motion associated with the removal and addition of density. At the same time, the center-of-mass moves smoothly. One cannot have both in the same world of the interval dx . The dx world, however, is an average world because it based on a measurement. Thus $P(x,p)dx=dx/L$ simply describes an average picture of dx which does not include an important part of the physics. Given that dx may be any size, however, the same constant average holds and so there seems to be an underlying process which creates this constant and is based on p and $-p$, because these disappear in $P(x,p)$.

As a result, it is possible mathematically to have ((2)) with $P_{\text{special}}(x,p) = \exp(ipx)$. X and p are physically known at the same time, it is just that x does not mean that the center-of-mass is definitely at this point. $\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of square root probability. The center-of-mass undergoes smooth motion and is associated with $P(x)dx=dx/L$. Nevertheless, $\exp(ipx)$ represents spatial probability associated with impulses, because the physical chunky periodic motion is associated with a momentum, whereas the smooth center-of-mass approach is an average. As a result, impulse interactions are described by $\exp(ipx)$ and one may then return to the averaged world of $P(x)dx=dx/L$ using the recipe:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad \text{and} \quad P(x) = W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((4))$$

It is interesting to note that $W(x)$ is not associated with any measurement interval dx , because it is linked with the intrinsic chunky periodic motion which is continuous. Each $\exp(ipx)$ has its own intrinsic length \hbar/p , called a wavelength. As a result, chunky periodic motion differs for different p values as does the impulse rendered by each p . We use p in the description, because one wishes to find a $P_{\text{special}}(p,x)$ which may be used to describe impulse reactions. $P=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ means that v_1 and v_2 being different still have the same p , and so one does not want to use velocity in the description.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classical mechanics seems to be based on the description of a particle, with some kind of shape, by a center-of-mass point. The focus is on the behaviour of this point based on a measurement type of scheme, namely a dx interval picture. In other words, the center-of-mass may be within a measurement segment dx . Within this segment changes may occur, but one only needs average values for dx , especially if it becomes very small. Thus, there is a $v(x)$, which again is based on a certain kind of discrete measurement, i.e. the center-of-mass enters dx at t_1 and leaves at t_2 . This is a measurement scenario, but does not include the continuous x details

which actually occur, it seems. In other words, it is an approximation. The idea is that by making dx approach 0, one has continuous motion, but this is a continuous description of the center-of-mass, not of the particle, we argue. In the case of constant motion, $P(x,p)=1/L$ and so is constant regardless of the size of dx . This suggests an underlying motion which creates this constant at each x point using p and $-p$, as p information disappears from $P(x,p)$.

We suggest that a particle is more complicated than simply its center-of-mass. We argue that motion is associated with a kind of chunky periodicity because density disappears from one region and appears in another. This is not the same physical process as translation of the center-of-mass. Mathematically, motion to the right or left is distinguished in the translation picture by the sign of dx , i.e. $+$ or $-$. Chunky periodicity, however, is not so simple. A perceived issue with chunky periodicity, however, is that it is continuous and not associated with the motion of a single point in a deterministic manner. The dx interval approach appears deterministic because it yields an average value ($v(x)$) at each dx , but this is only an average. We suggest that one cannot reject the chunky periodicity of motion and that it is different for forwards and backwards motion. How then may one reconcile this with the usual $P(x)dx=dx/L$ for the center-of-mass? We suggest that one must remove the chunkiness associated with the addition/removal of density and this seems to happen through:

$$P(x) = P_{\text{special}}(x,p)P_{\text{special}}(x,-p).$$

P_{special} is continuous and not associated with dx regions. $P_{\text{special}}(p, x)$ multiplied by $P_{\text{special}}(-p, x)$ yield a constant so that $P(x)$ is constant regardless of the dx interval used. In reality, however, $P_{\text{special}}(p, x)$ contains continuous x impulse information which describes interactions in a probabilistic way and includes physics which ignores this by only using averages within a dx region. In other words, the measurement associated with a dx picture loses information about the full physics present. One only needs to find equal hits in each dx region to conclude that $P(x,p)=1/L$. This is one kind of measurement, but a 2-slit interference measurement is a second and is very different. The second measurement picks up a feature of particle motion which is not noticed by the first measurement. The first measurement only notices that the particle is consistent with motion at a constant speed.

In particular, the chunky periodic approach yields a characteristic length \hbar/p , and so one cannot choose a measurement region smaller than this without removing important probabilistic information. This view treats $\exp(ipx)$ as a mathematical type of probability needed for impulse calculations without requiring interval measurements. The question: Which slit did the particle pass through is an interval type of question, we argue and does not account for the probability distribution in x associated with chunky periodic motion associated with adding and removing density.

References

1. Majernick, V. And Optarny T. Entropic Uncertainty Relations for a Quantum Oscillator (Journal of Physica A Mathematical and General, 1999)
(PDF) [Entropic uncertainty relations for a quantum oscillator \(researchgate.net\)](#)